

THE MORPHOLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE PARTS OF SPEECH IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida so'z turkumlari va uning xususiyatlarini ikki til kesimida o'xshash va qarama qarshi tomonlari taqqoslanadi. Shuningdek, Sharq va G'arb tilshunoslarining so'z turkumlari o'rganishda olib borgan izlanishlaridagi farqlar va o'xshashliklar ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Uning maqsadi, shuningdek so'z turkumlarining umumiy xususiyatlari va tarkibiy xilma-xilligini tavsiflash va tushuntirishdir.*

***Tayanch so'zlar:** so'z turkumlari, fel,ot,sifat, qiyosiy tipologiya va morfologiya.*

***Abstract:** This article compares the similarities and opposites of the parts of speech and its peculiarities in English and Uzbek languages. Also, the differences and similarities between Eastern and Western linguists in the study of parts of speech considered. Its purpose is also to describe and explain the common features and structural diversity of similarity and difference in two languages.*

***Key words:** grammatical category, parts of speech, verb, adjective, noun, adverb, comparative typology and morphology.*

Morphology studies how words are formed and varied. It studies the relationship between morphemes, and how morphemes can be put together to create new words, or new forms of the stem word.

There are two types of morphological relations: inflectional and derivational. When an inflectional affix is added to a stem word, a new form of the stem word is produced. When a derivational affix is added to a stem word, a new word with new meaning is produced. Affixes, such as prefixes and suffixes, are bound morphemes,

and are different from free morphemes. Free morphemes are lexical units, and when two free morphemes are put together, a compound word is produced.

Due to the way syntactic and lexical derivatives are represented, it often happens that a node's t-lemma differs from its m-lemma.

Complex nodes are divided into four basic groups (according to their tlemmas) which are further subdivided. These four basic groups are called semantic parts of speech. Semantic parts of speech are categories of the tectogrammatical level and correspond to the basic onomasiological categories: substances, properties, circumstances and events.

The part of speech¹ include the followings in English languages:

- noun;
- adjectives;
- verb;
- pronoun;
- numeral;
- adverb;
- interjection;
- conjunction;
- preposition;
- articles.

When it comes to the morphology, it analysis the structure and parts of words. To be more precise it analysis stems, root words, prefixes and suffixes. Another feature of the morphology in English language is that it studies parts of speech, intonation and stress. Moreover, the ways context changes a word's pronunciation and meaning are studied as well.

Precisely, Morphology studies how morphemes, parts of words, form various meanings by mixing with each other or standing alone. With the help of morphology, we can have a strong awareness of prefixes, suffixes and base words.

¹ Rijkhoff, Jan (2007). „, Word classes”

Additionally, the structures and meanings can be understood within words.

In English language, morphemes are divided into three main parts;

- Free and Bond;
- Derivational and Inflectional;
- Prefixes and Suffixes.

When we refer to “free morphemes”¹, we should think of an independent word that can be used alone, such as, university, woman, table, intelligent.

However, “Bond morphemes” only occur as part of a word. For instance, -ed as educate +ed.

Bond morpheme includes inflectional and derivational morphemes.

- Inflectional morphemes are suffixes which are, for example, -s, -ing, -ed.
- Derivational morphemes consist of prefixes. e.g.: de-, pre-, in-, un-.

On the other hand, in the Uzbek language, the parts of speech are divided into three main parts. They are the followings:

1) Mustaqil so‘zlar (independent words):

- noun;
- adjectives;
- numeral;
- verb;
- adverb;
- pronoun.

2) Oraliqdagi so‘zlar (middle words):

- exclamation (undov so‘zlar);
- modal;
- imitative words (taqlid so‘zlar)

3) Yordamchi so‘zlar (auxiliary words):

- Bog‘lovchi (conjunctions);
- Ko‘makchi (auxiliary words);

¹ Kroeger, Paul (2005). *Analysing Grammar: An introduction*, Cambridge University press. P. 13. ISBN 978-0-52101653-7.

– Yuklama (exclamations).

Words can change according to the morphological features. For example:

e.g.: Uy-uylar, home-homes.

e.g.: Salim bugun ukasiga beshta daftar oldi;

e.g.: Salim has bought 5 copy books to his brother today.

Here – “Salim, bugun, daftar, uka, ol”, are independent words, whereas *-i*, *-ga*, *-di* are the suffixes which do not mean anything when they come alone.

Semantically, in English grammar sentences structure includes the arrangement of words, phrases and clauses¹.

Semantic features basic components of meaning in any lexis.

Semantic features help to explain meaning and their contrast. It shows how words are both similar and different which puts an emphasis on the uniqueness of each words.

Actually, the part-of-speech consists of 2 main groups.

- 1) Major word-classes: nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs.
- 2) Minor word-classes: articles, prepositions, conjunctions, interjections.

All members of all major word-class share a distinguishing semantic component as a lexical one of a part-of-speech meaning: nouns have the meaning of thingness or substantiality, though they possess different grammatical meanings of number and case.

Semantics are united in terms of grammatical meaning.

Syntactic parts of speech. The term syntactic part of speech refers to the role of a word in the sentence. The fact that a word belongs to a syntactic part-of speech is not encoded in any attribute of the word; the term is used exclusively to make the explanation of the difference between the semantic and traditional parts of speech easier.

1. *NOUN* is the name of a person, place, thing, or idea. For example: *man*, *butter*, *college*, *house*, *happiness* and the like.

¹ Partee, B., Semantics in R. A. Wilson and F.C. Keil . Press. 1999. P 739-742.

A noun is a word for a person, place, thing, or idea. Nouns are often used with an article (the, a, an), but not always. Proper nouns always start with a capital letter; common nouns do not. Nouns can be singular or plural, concrete or abstract. Nouns show possession by adding 's. Nouns can function in different roles within a sentence; for example, a noun can be a subject, direct object, indirect object, subject complement, or object of a preposition.

The young girl brought me a very long letter from the teacher, and then she quickly disappeared. Oh my!

2. *PRONOUN*. A pronoun is a word used in place of a noun.

A pronoun is a word used in place of a noun. A pronoun is usually substituted for a specific noun, which is called its antecedent. In the sentence above, the antecedent for the pronoun she is the girl. Pronouns are further defined by type: personal pronouns refer to specific persons or things; possessive pronouns indicate ownership; reflexive pronouns are used to emphasize another noun or pronoun; relative pronouns introduce a subordinate clause; and demonstrative pronouns identify, point to, or refer to nouns.

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3. *VERB*

A verb expresses action or being.

jump... is... write... become

The verb in a sentence expresses action or being. There is a main verb and sometimes one or more helping verbs. ("She can sing." Sing is the main verb; can is the helping verb.) A verb must agree with its subject in number (both are singular or both are plural). Verbs also take different forms to express tense.

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See the TIP Sheet on "Verbs" for more information.

4. *ADJECTIVE*

An adjective modifies or describes a noun or pronoun.

pretty... old... blue... smart

An adjective is a word used to modify or describe a noun or a pronoun. It usually answers the question of which one, what kind, or how many. (Articles [a, an, the] are usually classified as adjectives.)

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See the TIP Sheet on "Adjectives" for more information.

5. *ADVERB*

An adverb modifies or describes a verb, an adjective, or another adverb.

gently... extremely... carefully... well

An adverb describes or modifies a verb, an adjective, or another adverb, but never a noun. It usually answers the questions of when, where, how, why, under what conditions, or to what degree. Adverbs often end in -ly.

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See the TIP Sheet on "Adverbs" for more information.

6. *PREPOSITION*

A preposition is a word placed before a noun or pronoun to form a phrase modifying another word in the sentence.

by... with.... about... until

(by the tree, with our friends, about the book, until tomorrow)

A preposition is a word placed before a noun or pronoun to form a phrase modifying another word in the sentence. Therefore a preposition is always part of a prepositional phrase. The prepositional phrase almost always functions as an adjective or as an adverb. The following list includes the most common prepositions:

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See the TIP Sheet on "Prepositions" for more information.

7. *CONJUNCTION*

A conjunction joins words, phrases, or clauses.

and... but... or... while... because

A conjunction joins words, phrases, or clauses, and indicates the relationship between the elements joined. Coordinating conjunctions connect grammatically equal elements: and, but, or, nor, for, so, yet. Subordinating conjunctions connect clauses that are not equal: because, although, while, since, etc. There are other types of conjunctions as well.

The young girl brought me a very long letter from the teacher, and then she quickly disappeared. Oh my!

See the TIP Sheet on "Conjunctions" for more information.

8. *INTERJECTION*

An interjection is a word used to express emotion.

Oh!... Wow!... Oops!

An interjection is a word used to express emotion. It is often followed by an exclamation point.

The young girl brought me a very long letter from the teacher, and then she quickly disappeared. Oh my! For example, substantivity is for nouns, verbality is for verbs, quality is for adjectives, the quality of the quality is for adverbs, numbers is for numerals, state is for statives. This means that semantics is the grammatical meaning of the whole class of words, general grammatical meaning.

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